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Rethinking ICT Innovations in the Critical Environment of Scholarly Publishing: Exploring New Discursive/Literary Directions for an Open-Sourced Digital Model

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Abstract

This study set out to address the question of digital scholarly publishing in the broad context of socio-institutional and historical construction. The purpose of the study is therefore to show that the 'Gutenberg revolution' has not yet been attained for digital scholarly publishing because of the environmental subjectivities of society, political economy and discourse that deconstruct its trajectory of innovative disruption. The main methods deployed were the social shaping of technology and the embeddedness paradigms. They enable the study to move beyond narrow, technological readings to scrutinize broader sociological implications for cyberspace publishing. Consequently, it found out that since the 1980s, digitization has only changed the process of scientific communication but has hardly made a significant dent on the substance of academic communication. It is very prone to risks from the 'square peg' and 'horseless carriage' models of understanding its progression. The tendency now is for digital publishing to take the direction of concentration and restrictions and because of the embeddedness of the digital in the social and the discursive contexts; its growth is deeply contingent upon historical and contemporary institutional structures.

Keywords

Digital scholarly publishing, innovations, social shaping of informatics, the myth of technological revolutions, critical environment, discourse

INTRODUCTION

The internet and ICTs were invented as a technology in the publishing of scholarly documents because of the high cost and slow pace of accessing the knowledge capital and resource prompted attempts to replace paper publishing with electronic dissemination. A number of economic models were adopted to sustain the process. This included charging the author (as opposed to the reader) who benefitted from publishing his documents. Digitization of publishing made information to be linkable, searchable, and enabled readers to read in a wiki-styled way with possibilities of having immediate feedback. However, historically, the economic, social, cultural and historical context of the transition from publishing to digitization has been extremely troubled because it comes with risks, the challenge of concentration, the myth of technological revolutions and disembeddedness of historical considerations. This paper argues that scientific innovations of communication in scholarly publishing such as e-journals, virtual journals, portals, etc, are not determined solely by information and communication technologies but rather by contexts of political economy and critical discourse. In the past, the invention of printing itself did not occasion the 'Gutenberg revolution' of the scientific journal, but was predicated on two hundred years of multiple transformations out with the facilitation of the printing press, The medium of the printing press did not cause the advent of scientific publishing but only induced effects that stimulated its realization in terms of its power to distribute content to a wider and larger audience, to disseminate content that was not exclusively religious nor exclusively scholarly, and so on. The scientific journal took considerable time to establish itself as the major medium over the monograph and to evolve into its standardized form in the Twentieth century.

Media do not transform the practices of science nor of scientific communication; rather, requirements for communication change and the practice of research eventually construct the selection of a medium, or the development of one, for the facilitation of its closure. Even innovative technology may fail to be disruptive (Kling et al. 2003, Christensen 2006). Technology is signified as a 'solution' when it is *interpreted as such* and

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adopted by society, when societal actors make sense of it and accept it as the appropriate opportunity among other options. In this way, closure is an evolutionary process that is sluggish in accommodation and slow in adaption to external factors. There are distinctive development paths that processes of innovation diffusion follow and they may either lead to failure, rejection or widespread adoption. Scientific publishing is a political process where power relations and agents of change play important roles. By themselves, the technical properties and merits of digital publishing technologies account, in very limited ways, for their success; rather, the larger proportion of factors that determine success or failure are in the domains of society and critical discursivity.

This paper is therefore premised on the hypothesis that web technologies and the internet deployed in scholarly publications are not merely abstract constructs with intrinsic properties of their own, acting as agents of change with the potential to influence their environments and trigger a revolution, but, are rather determined by existential factors of political economy and discursivity. In the concept of technological determinism, there is a failure to consider the manifold interdependencies and discursive interactions that exist between technologies and social context. The process of technological innovation should be perceived less in terms of components and procedures, which are technologically determined for the most part, and more in the light of their embodiments and applications in social infrastructures and their adoption by actors, who are socially and discursively contextualized. Digital technology in scholarly publications is constructed by a broader process of social shaping of technology (Kling et al. 2003, Christensen 2006, Christensen and Bower, Gunn 2000, Harnad 1991). The content of the innovations and the technologies are embedded in socio-economic patterns, rather than in an inner technical logic itself; that content is a social product patterned by the conditions of its creation and use. Now, this study is important because, beyond narrow technological considerations, each stage in the creation and implementation of new technologies engages with a set of choices between options that are discursively interpreted, as well as a set of social factors that affect the selection of options, their configurability and their social implications for the content of technology. Digital technologies are a system of work organization and control involving negotiations over priorities and goals that are intellectualized. Innovations of digital technologies can only be adopted, for example, if they are perceived to be beneficiary, and are seen as not violating the cultural norms of a community.

The purpose of this paper is to investigate the troubled innovative environment of digitization of scholarly publishing by analyzing the risks, the challenge of concentration, the myth of technological revolutions and disembeddedness of historical considerations. This is significant because the digital technology of publishing does not function in a vacuum: to understand how we can make real progress in the publishing sector, we have to comprehend the 'bigger picture' that complexities and may minimize or even threaten its functioning. Therefore, it asks the question: what are the sociological conditions that construct digital publishing?

Current scholarship tends to focus narrowly on the assessment and importance of digital publishing to universities and the teaching faculty (Brown, Griffiths, Rascoff and Guthrie 2007), types of digital resources for publishing (Maron and Smith 2008), broadening the spectrum of publishing in the digital age (Warren 2010), the relationship between scholarly practice and participatory technologies and explore how such technologies invite and reflect the emergence of a new form of digital scholarship on open source (Veletsianos and Kimmons 2012, Harnad et al. 2012, Jeffery 2006).

The paper ends with the proposition that, in spite of these complex environmental issues, there are also opportunities that can serve as drivers toward an open sourced model of e-publishing.

2. METHOD

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In order to realize this paper, we deployed insights from the social shaping of technology theory and critical embedded theory (Bijker and Law 1992, Beer and Berry 2014, Callon 2012, Williams 1997, Williams and Edge 1996, Giles, 1996). These theories hold that stages in the process of technological innovation should be seen in the light of increasing contextualization. Whereas components and procedures are technologically determined to a great extent, their embodiment and application, as well as their large scale adoption, are determined by social context. The different paradigms that go beyond the technical properties of technology can be listed under the broader theory of the social shaping of technology. A variety of scholarships with different intellectual traditions and preoccupations, maintain that technology's 'black-box' has to be opened to enable the exposure and analysis of socio-economic patterns embedded in the processes of innovation and in the content of technologies.

ICTs were supposed to induce a revolution in scientific communication comparable to the Gutenberg revolution; however, that revolution became more of a myth than reality (Borgman 2003). The digital medium has not yet caused a scientific revolution. From historical experience, media does not necessarily change the practices of scientific communication nor of science itself. With developments in research practice, and as requirements for communication transformation, appropriate media for communication are developed when they are inexistent or selected when available. Thus practice comes first before closure; technological closure does not come first before practice. In other words, social readings, sense creation and acceptance come first before the adoption of a particular technological solution as opposed to other available solutions. Technological closure is an evolutionary process of adaptation and accommodation to external factors that is slow in relative terms. Processes of innovation diffusion often follow a distinctive development path leading either to failure, rejection or general adoption. The development of digital technology is not simplistically a question of technology; it is more critically a political process where agents of change and relationships of power play an important role. The potentiality of success for digital technology, its futuristic usage and its impactability are less a function of its technical merits and properties and more a question of social and historical context. Technology is not an abstract construct that acts as an/the agent of change and exerts influence on its environment. Consequently, it is not logical to speak of the results of digital influences in the light of revolutions, that is, of basic transformations that take place thanks to the intrinsic properties of the technology. Change cannot be predicated on digital determinism, but rather on various forms of interdependencies and interactivities between the technology and social environment. It is false to speak of the inevitability of digital technological outcomes, the logic of its effects for society or of activism destined to promote unavoidable developments in order to undertake a fight against conservative forces.

This paper is a rethinking of this utopian rhetoric surrounding ICTs and publishing. Technology does not develop following certain inner technical logic, but rather, it is a *social product* that is patterned in accordance with the conditions of its conception and employment. Every phase in the creation and application of new technologies engages with a set of choices between various technical preferences. Thus, in addition to technical considerations, there are other social factors that impact on the selection of options and have effects on technological content and its social implications. Unless the printing press, digital technologies are configured by being adapted to particularities of social contexts. ICTs and publishing are much more prone to being shaped, used and accommodated in various ways according to context. Digital innovations should be seen more in terms of increasing levels of contextualization. There is no inescapable and direct link between digital innovations and the practice of scientific communications. Digital innovations can be adopted only if they benefit readers and authors and if they do not infringe on the conventions and norms of the scientific community. Innovations have nothing to do with how an author argues, stylizes or presents his book or paper, but pertains to the level of how the book or paper is distributed by infrastructures and how that distribution is accepted by the scientific or academic community. As innovation theory instructs us, at the level of scientific

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and academic communication, the tendency is for innovation to be successful at the aggregate level of infrastructures than at the level of communication practice of individual academics and scientists.

3.0 RESULTS

3.1 Digital Innovations at Informal and Formal levels of Scientific Communication

ICT innovations have been able to exert impact chiefly at the informal level of communications such as products derived from information like virtual journals, portals and email lists. Sources of data that are functioning at the input stage of research also belong to this category. ICT use has a significant impact on the productivity of academics and scientists and this effect can be attributed principally to informal communication. Kaminer and Braunstein (1998) carried out a bibliometric study that showed that only 9% of the employment of the digital technology was focused on collecting formal scientific information via e-journals (Kaminer and Braunstein 1998). The innovations that ICTs provide and are applied to formal scientific communication and the peer reviewed article impact chiefly in the area of network transmission mode rather than in the print mode itself. For example, what is often considered as ‘e-journals’ is actually the digital edition of printed copies of already existing journals with their printed papers. There are very few ‘e-only’ journals that exist as a result of digital innovations.

Ever since the 1980s, digitization has only changed the process of scientific communication but has hardly made a significant dent on the substance of academic communication. For example, it has become easier and faster to distribute and access academic and scientific documents through processes such as browsing and searching. Digitization has facilitated communication at the levels of libraries, journals and publishers. However, digitization has not changed the nature of the scientific paper as a unit of communication, although efforts were made to innovate e-only journals that can transform the scientific and academic paper into a new digital genre. Digitization has transformed the input stage of research, in terms of how scientists acquire information, but, at the output level, has not transformed basically how scientists and academics report on the results of their research projects. E-journals are accepted by the scientific and academic community because they facilitate access (anytime, anywhere) and add operability at the aggregate level (Rusch-Feja and Siebecky 1999).

Digitization of the research journal is now constructing changes in practices of research. The search for subjects in digital collections of journals implied that the researcher had to cross various disciplinary borders quite easily than when the search was being done through print collections. As a result, multidisciplinary research was boosted (Rusch-Feja and Siebecky 1999). E-journal’s intertextuality enabled digitization to add active hyperlinks and other operationalities between information sources and articles and between articles themselves. Documents carry knowledge and the challenge is not only to choose relevant documents but also to retrieve and extract relevant knowledge from the documents. Because users are checking out not only on facts but also on knowledge claims that are substantiated, they tend to be interested in information that provides background through texts, documents and other forms of communication (Hjørland 2000). Thanks to cross-linking, search functions, etc, the digital information system provides something that goes beyond content to the context at an aggregate level. This evidences the fact that the scientific journal is embedded in the network of social contexts and cannot be seen as simply existing and functioning in a vacuum.

3.2 Risks: The ‘Square Peg’ and ‘Horseless Carriage’ Models of Assessments

There is the risk that if the information is published without the benefit of peer-review, information may be devalued. The monopoly that scientific journals, with their peer-review institutions, had over the publication of information is being lost. The revenue models that maintained the review and publishing process are being eroded. The cases of promotion and tenure may be hampered because of the loss of tracking bibliographic

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citations. The older publication model may be rendered inaccessible as a result of the loss of archiving, revenue models. An even greater risk is that social media are now the ‘horseless carriage’ of scholarly publishing. In one sense, the deployment of digitization can be seen as misdirected because it does not quite fit into the processes that have classically comprised scholarly publishing. The challenge is how to adapt digitization to the existing practices of scholarly publishing such as knowledge archiving and tracking, accreditation, acceptance, copyright issues and so forth. Underpinning this challenge is the idea that the ‘square peg’ of digital technology should be made to become ‘round’ so that it can fit into the ‘round hole’ of current practice. But an even greater challenge is the ‘horseless carriage’ perspective in which digitization serves precisely to change practice. The new media may be a viable alternative to the current model of scholarly publishing, which it is out to transform given what can be seen as its backward and obsolete practices. Digitization has the potential to change scholarly publishing beyond simply substituting physical with electronic paper. It can transform what we even understand by knowledge, how we produce it, use it, communicate it, etc. Digitization can change the task to which it is implemented. Social media can potentially change scholarly publishing.

Cell phones, internet, RSS feeds, camera phones, iPods, podcasts, blogs and computer games are changing traditional publishing modes as they enable anyone to publish their works for an international readership. Readers can as well access a huge body of knowledge at no charge or for a very minimal cost and by so doing they bypass the services of publishers. The technologies are altering the flow of information from a unidirectional to a multi-directional flux with the blurring of the difference between author and reader. With the convergence of knowledge production and consumption, new technologies are now creating the potential for new knowledge practices that are also fuelling scientific research. The digitization of knowledge production, conveyance and consumption are not only having an effect on scholarly publishing, but it is also impacting on the modalities of its practice, notably, the economic, social, cultural and legal modalities, the publishing institutions and practitioners themselves and the societies of knowledge. No one discipline nor segment of society can provide adequate answers to all the questions asked; rather, answers must come from multiple stakeholders.

For example, when the University of California Centre for New Media was created, the objective was to convene experts in different disciplinary areas, in order to inquire into various themes from various viewpoints. Although this approach does not guarantee adequate answers, it sets the setting for searching for them. The University of California Berkeley Centre for New Media associated with a major scientific publisher, Elsevier, to summon conferences entitled as ‘Information Dynamics Workshops’ aimed at exposing how new media open up opportunities for the publishing industry and the implications of these opportunities for this sector (Brooks and Arcuni 2019). In 2006, a workshop was organized with thirty scholars attending from fifteen disciplines. The selected themes for the workshop focused on the effects of new media on personal information behaviour and practices of academics in terms of gathering, filtering, customizing, personalizing and dissemination of information. The effects of new media on scholarly publications within specific research groups were discussed as a theme. Lastly, the perception of digital publications, archiving and technological research was also discussed as a theme.

The system of scientific publishing is the major backbone of the production of knowledge, the verification process and the tenure and promotion system in higher education institutions, particularly. As a result, academic journals constructed their reputations by publishing quality papers, and sustaining the credence of the scientists and knowledge they published. So, the relationship between author and publisher was one of mutual benefit in which the author contributed knowledge, peer-reviewed it and the publisher valorized it by collecting, printing, managing, disseminating, archiving and tracking it through the economic model of subscription. Although this scientific publishing model was subjected to criticism because knowledge creation and acquisition were paid for through the authors and via subscription, attempts to replace this model with a

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better one failed until the digital model came to threaten its essential characteristics.

The internet and new media offered a viable alternative to this model by enabling authors to publish knowledge on their personal and institutional websites. Readers were able to access knowledge at little or no cost and, in this way, both authors and readers were able to bypass publishers. Although the digital model was economically viable, it ignored many socio-cultural aspects of scholarly publishing such as knowledge accreditation, tracking and archiving. The digital model did not know the role that knowledge accreditation, tracking and archiving played in establishing personal careers and constructing scientific societies. This is consistent with the theory that the technology had the potential to facilitate certain aspects of the scholarly publishing practice (the 'square peg') and could harm or even ignore other vital aspects (the horseless carriage).

3.3 From Ownership to Licensing

The networking and digitization of scholarly documents have resulted in licensing in which access to digitized scholarly knowledge on publisher servers is leased out. Consequently, a librarian has to rely on networked access to a digital library instead of purchasing CD-ROMS or paper. Publishers now create greater restrictions than those that were protected by US copyright laws, for example, including restricted uses that were protected under the Fair use principle. Given that the employment of the digital technology involves creating a copy of a work by downloading a document from a server, the argument being put forward is that greater restrictions are being enforced than could be placed on paper work (Lessig 1999, Lariviere, Haustein, and Mongeon 2015). The licensing of materials means the loss of perpetual access in the context of scholarly publishing. In the case of paper, if a library cancels subscriptions, users are still entitled to their purchased volumes. In the case of digital libraries, when one stops paying, one loses access to content, especially if it was not saved or printed.

Owing to preoccupations with unauthorized copying, some publishers acquired computer software/hardware tools or technological protection measures, which are designed to restrict access to the use of works (Eschenfelder, Desai and Downey 2010). In order to restrict the employment of protected digital materials, technological protection measures were implemented in conjunction with the 1998 Digital Millennium Copyright Act anti-circumvention provisions and license restrictions (Burk 2003). Technological protection measures were seen to facilitate new business models that could not be possible with some form of control. Other arguments were that publishers might refuse to distribute valuable documents online, unless they can assure themselves that it will not be poorly employed. Technological protection measures also guaranteed a return on investment (Durrance 2008). Questions of control became more important than in previous years because scholarly publishing expanded its customer base into the international markets with various norms of social copying. The 2011 International Intellectual Property Alliance 301 Chinese report draws attention to the usage of journals and books in universities and to piracy of library academic journals (International Intellectual Property Alliance 2010). Technological protection measures control document access by controlling who can log into a digital library, who is employing a particular computer or login credential. Scholarly publishers applied the requirement of page-by-page printing as another type of technological protection measures in order to make copying costly (Eschenfelder 2008).

3.4 Embeddedness of the Digital in Historical and Contemporary Structures

In order to critically comprehend, for example, the Norwegian book industry, one has to understand industry structure in terms of ownership, degree of vertical and horizontal integration, cross-ownership, mergers, collaboration, acquisitions and so forth, and this applies as well to the other media industries, which are established and mature and are industries dominated by legacy players. One has to comprehend the place of industry associations and unions, as well as the role of spokespersons permitted to negotiate on behalf of the

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industry such as publishers (Bolter & Grusin 1999, Stewart, Proctor, Williams and Poschen 2008). Understanding digitization of scholarly publishing signifies coming to terms with organizational structure, that is, with how media organizations select to perform certain tasks engaged with digitalization. More specifically, it has to do with the creation of formal structures (departments, projects, editorial divisions), the degree of or in-house labour and outsourcing, consideration of how many people are involved, who they are, how management is involved, etc.

Although technology is the chief factor in understanding digitalization thanks to its software formats, hardware platforms, its standards and practices, one has to go beyond these to see that the media industry executive is faced with an important number of various technological options, for example, of re-mediation, in which the old media is still relevant (Bolter & Grusin 1999). The choice of one option over another can have certain consequences. There are the structure and the dynamics of digital marketplaces, which are linked to industry formations and technology. The digitalization of publishing constructs borders new ambiguities between markets that were hitherto distinct. New distribution barriers have emerged which can be managed although cultural and linguistic barriers are still significant for the demarcation of markets. The technical aspect of digitalization (digitization) also signifies a potential for converging media forms, leading to content classes like game apps, book apps, and so forth.

Any institutional framework which does not consider policy issues as a facet would obscure the place of state institutions. For example, in the Norwegian context, substantial state programmes of direct and indirect subsidies incentivize innovation and competition (Colbjørnsen 2014). From the viewpoint of digitalization, the differential treatment of analogue and digital products and services in the light of value added tax is instructive. The financial assistance of the state signifies that legitimization work is a key preoccupation of spokespersons of the media industry, both in public debate and in direct political lobbying. Therefore digital media is embedded in state structures and policies (Granovetter 1985, Grünberg & Pallas 2013, Orlikowski 1992, Orlikowski 2000).

The issue of ‘square peg’ and ‘horseless carriage’ is critical because it raises a set of other questions: first, what precisely is ‘scholarly publishing’ and what is its social role? If it is defined simply as a technology of distribution of knowledge from an author to a reader, then the digital technology plays the role well by substituting physical paper with digital modes of communication. However, the definition of scholarly publishing is much more complex because, beyond distribution, it has to do with the social creation and guardianship of knowledge. Publishers in this model are gatekeepers of the social institutions of knowledge, who render knowledge credible by managing and organizing it via the process of peer review. Publishers also transform knowledge into cultural capital. This is where the second assessment, the ‘horseless carriage’ evaluation is relevant, namely, that digitization ignores socio-cultural aspects of scholarly publishing, and may even harm other important aspects that are necessary for its long term sustainability. The technological definition is too narrow a perspective from which to consider digitization because, more critically, it has a collaborative role in the process of social communication. More precisely, it has to create, validate and archive the cultural capital called knowledge.

Digitization of scholarly publishing is not merely about innovative technologies like the electronic distribution of articles; beyond electronic delivery, it is much more about the social creation and guardianship of information and knowledge. In the current model of digitization of scholarly publishing, publishers try to amalgamate both roles of gatekeeping the peer review process of organizing and managing, the social institutions that provide knowledge with trustworthiness and transform knowledge into cultural capital. The digitization of scholarly publishing, which consists of introducing new media to substitute paper distribution with electronic distribution cannot efficiently handle all the sociological aspects of scholarly publishing. In order to really appreciate the effects of the introduction of new media on personal information behaviour, it is

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necessary to revisit the knowledge rationalization process, otherwise knowledge would lose its value and credibility. In order to address this sociological aspect of scientific publishing, some efforts were made to replace the centralization of editorial curatorship based on a self-selected corps of scholars charged with reviewing, verifying and correcting information with a model of distribution contingent upon the social consciousness of authors and critics.

The Open Source Initiative, Creative Commons and Wikipedia attempted to validate the scholar's individual activity as opposed to the editorial board's institutional agency. Although these efforts yielded the necessary democratization of information collection, there are still serious challenges of proper 'sourcing' which is a requisite condition for the scientific community to validate a paper as 'high quality'. This lack of accreditation through a seal of approval prompted other efforts to address the problem such as employment of the popularity criterion with Amazon.com ranking of books according to the number sold, the voting system based on reliability in e-Bay and the use of links from Google's search engine web pages displayed on screens. It is necessary to associate information and value, although, even at this level, new questions still arise such as the signifying differentiation between credibility and popularity. It is not necessarily plausible to state that a paper that has been downloaded a thousand times is more valuable and credible than one that is downloaded a hundred times.

The changes in the nature of scholarly materials were as a result of the fact that end users valued networking access and speed over the physical ownership of materials. In the mindsets of end users, the value of physical ownership decreased and the concept of 'convenience' changed its significance from citation to full text access in an instant manner without the need for physical movements. Even though services of digital libraries and SAE materials were very expensive in comparison to databases and print materials, it was the will of users that became the decisive factor than the financial impediments. The Open Access movement was made possible thanks to the social assumptions that emerged in the 2000s according to which open access to research results would ameliorate public health in all nation states, increase economic growth and democratize nations all over the world. This rhetoric impacted greatly on the expectations of end users and, this, in turn, compelled publishers to give a different treatment to scholarly materials. Although a European Union Report acknowledged an open source agenda, the transition to an open science has been very challenging (Van Norden 2013). The old, monolithic school of publishing has not yet been completely disrupted. Publishers provide basic services to the research community while, at the same time, holding them hostage. Nevertheless, there are emerging oligopolies that are fragmented and offer various services and business models. For example, ResearchGate, Google Scholar and Mendeley are some of the stakeholders that offer free and quality services (Mendeley 2016).

From the viewpoint of scholarly materials and changes to their nature, the media networking and ICTs created new products that were referred to as 'digital libraries' (e.g. JSTOR, Elsevier's Science Direct) much valued by libraries and publishers because they provided search services and network based access to content databases (Polanyi 1957). Digital libraries completely revolutionized the ways users valued and employed scholarly materials. Before the 1990s, digital libraries did not store full texts but citations. Users were required to obtain the citations from the digital libraries and make copies of the desired content by going to a library that had subscribed to a physical copy of the preferred journal. Prior to this year, the user could go to a library and obtain a requested article and they appreciated the comprehensiveness of physical collections owned by their libraries. But digital libraries changed what users preferred, how they employed it and even what they could prefer. Insights into what constitutes convenience and what does not constitute expediency were completely transformed. Digital libraries enabled users to access full texts and a broader range of materials than could be bought on paper. They made networking more handy and integrated search tools, new indexing and hyperlinked interfaces that enabled researchers to browse for articles with speed. In the years the 2000s, digitization

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triggered the Open Access movement. Networking then created new opportunities for the outputs of scholarship to be freely accessed (Tenopir and King 1997).

The turbulent environment of digital publishing has been one of the discursivity and explosion of digitized services. Discursivity can be defined as shifts in meaning; it is about new openings and the emergence of multiple possibilities. Web 2.0. offered emergent and radical innovations particularly from the years the 2000s that burgeoned initiatives aimed at exploring new ways of producing and disseminating knowledge. These innovations were propelled by various social groups like start-ups, new entrants in the medicine industry, technology and science, etc, which focused on registration and dissemination of scientific findings through various platforms. Wikis and blogs (e.g. ScienceBlog) were created and maintained to develop a social reputation. Mega-journals that were peer-reviewed and open sourced were created. New actors and traditional publishers as well as established new forms of quality evaluation of scientific knowledge through blind review processes and double or triple blind and collaborative review processes. The Public Library of Science (PLOS ONE 2016), a non profit scientific association, published a well known online journal named PLOS ONE, an open access, open peer review, post-publication and community based journal. While citation and bibliographic databases had become the traditional practice, tagging and social bookmarking services became popular as well and were adopted by the scientific publishing industry and traditional publishing organizations as well. Tagging and social bookmarking services like Connotea, CiteULike and Del.icio.us (Delicious 2016) enabled scientific publications to be shared and recommended by users. Joshua Schachter created Del.icio.us in 2003 and was bought by both Yahoo and Science Inc in 2005 and 2014 respectively. Nature Publishing Group created in 2004 a reference management service that was free online called Connotea but by 2014, it was discontinued because of the wide availability of social media tools for scientists (Tenopir and King 2000, SCImago 2016).

In addition to the traditional citation-based metrics such as the Impact Factor, h-index and the SCImago Journal Ranking created in 2007, new metrics based on reputation mechanisms of impact evaluation, social bookmarking, suggestions and downloads, were explored as innovations and referred to as altmetrics (SCImago 2016). But even these metrics were found to be wanting because they simply endorsed the old scientific standards and did not consider the exigencies of the new practices of scholarship. The next critical question that emerged was how is scientific knowledge searches for, indexed and archived. Of course, ICT played a role in facilitating this radical thinking and transformation openings, but it took the human factor of dedicated new actors motivated to invest and derive profit such as the Google group that developed Google Scholar to track social interests through a number of readers, downloads, sharing, and so forth. Other perspectives emerged from here such as self-archiving of digital works. Mendeley was created as a web and desktop programme in order to search for data and manage or share research papers. It started as a small but promising project in 2007, but there were new social actors like Elsevier that wanted to aggrandize it, so in 2013, Elsevier bought it for this purpose of enhancement. The next challenge was that users, like scholars, needed to interact among themselves as they explored knowledge, and in order to facilitate this process, social network websites like Academia.com were created and they become very popular with users.

5.0 CONCLUSION

Quite often, the effects of digital technologies in the media industries are considered disruptive and revolutionary. I have argued in this paper that instead of thinking of digitalization as an object that acts upon its subject as an external force, we should see it as embedded within an environmental dynamic that is very complex because it embraces various contexts. This view is suggested to be considered as founded on a notion of digitalization as a process that is not merely technological, but also influenced by other factors beyond technological developments, that have to do with broader cultural, social, economic and other factors.

The idea of embeddedness and the theoretical frameworks of social shaping of technology and institutional

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paradigm provided ways of re-thinking (digital) technology, as enmeshed in institutions, sociological and cultural, to paraphrase Karl Polanyi (Polanyi 1957).

In spite of its vulnerability to the environment, a number of drivers were found to be supporting change toward digitization of publishing in the future. First, there is a shift from the physical process of issues of publication to a web-based, process of showcasing that is disrupting physical barriers and paper-based promotion. The search for scientific knowledge should shift from being a journal (and therefore publisher-) based on being more interactive and web-based. Interactivity should focus more on topic, content and author of the knowledge. A number of mechanisms have been created online to manage reputation and visibility and are being explored. Plagiarized scientific papers were found to have been published without transparency of data and results; however, such fake papers are being retracted online (Tenopir and King, 1997, 2000, SCiGen 2016).

Thus, one can state here that ICTs made it possible for new modes of publishing and new services to become available and widespread. These services included specialized online libraries, online degree services, healthcare platforms and medical databases, learning platforms and simulating/training software. However, these modes of publishing and new services were able to embrace disruptive innovations and yet avoid disruptions because they were socially constructed. They were put into the hands of new players, who made the services freely and widely available. Actors transformed these services from their first stage where initiatives were sparse to the next ones where they burgeoned. They came with philosophy and mindset of innovation with the risk of disruption. But their agile and alert minds prevented this prospect by not only shifting from the traditional practices but by also taking notice of new trends and responding efficiently to them in ways that were impactful. The technological platforms were converted into commercial services, some of which were managed autonomously while others were incorporated into new service portfolios, which, in turn, expanded into further concentrations. So, just as the print did not necessarily lead to the Gutenberg revolution (Giles 1996), in the same manner, the digitization of publishing has not led to an open source of publishing, for reasons that have to do, not with the technology itself, but with its embeddedness in societal subjectivities, political economy and discourse (Polanyi 1957).

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Sketch Bio

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